

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The effect of archivist competency and commitment on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(03), 587–597

Publication history: Received on 02 February 2023; revised on 11 March 2023; accepted on 14 March 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.3.0422>

Abstract

The research delivers an analysis of the partial and simultaneous effects of archivist competency and commitment on archive digitalization. It was descriptive research using a quantitative approach. Data were collected using questionnaires having been tested for validity and reliability. The results demonstrated that (1) archivist competency had a positive and significant effect on archive digitalization at a partial determination of 15.7%, (2) archivist commitment had a positive and significant effect on archive digitalization at a partial determination of 38.1%, and (3) archivist competency and commitment had a simultaneous positive and significant effect on archive digitalization. As regards the coefficient of determinant, the Adjusted R-Square was 0.519. The figure exhibited that archivist competency and commitment could elucidate archive digitalization variability in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo by 51.9%. Based on the results, as featured in the partial determination of each variable, the archivist commitment was more dominant in affecting the implementation of archive digitalization management than archivist competency. And yet, archivist competency also contributed to defining successful archive digitalization management.

Keywords: Archive Digitalization; Descriptive Quantitative Research; Archivist Commitment Effect; Archivist Competency Effect

1. Introduction

Organizations, in carrying out their activities, generate archives. Accordingly, archives are organizations' by-products. With the running of organizations, more archives will be produced. As organizations call for archives as the information about planning, decision-making, accountability, and historical evidence, archives demand good management. When entailing the archives, hence, organizations can find the information easily.

Archives are an unsegregated part of organizations. In other words, during their lives, organizations will result in archives. Barthos (2013:2) argue that archive management is an institution which conducts recording, handling, storing, and maintaining letters or scripts with imperative meanings by applying certain accountable discretion and systems. Archives, by functions, are divided into two, i.e., dynamic and static. Dynamic archives were used in planning and administrating a national life in general or state administration. Meanwhile, static archives are not directly employed in planning and administrating a national life or daily state administration.

Archive processing, which may take a long and complex process, if unsupported by managing competency and commitment, will unlikely run optimally. Dynamic archive management is arduous and, in so doing, entails competency and commitment. It is because dynamic archives nourish a life cycle consistent with the managing unit needs. Additionally, dynamic archives are important for organizational activities.

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Archive management is a complicated activity which requires competent and committed archivists. Archivists should handle recording, controlling, distributing, storing, maintaining, supervising, transferring, and destructing archives. The work covers the life cycle of archives (Amsyah, 2003:13).

Archivists play an indispensable role in assisting organizations in achieving visions and missions. Organizations, to augment archivist performance, should be supported by several components, e.g., competency. Competency constitutes knowledge, ability, and skill called for to conduct an undertaking. It establishes archivist performance characters engendering excellent outcomes. Government or private institutions as organizations, as such, need to assert competency necessity. With competency in archive management, archivists will be able to cope with technology advancement and exert it as a performance-supporting tool.

The key to successful archive digitalization is archivist resources. Hence, combating issues in digitalization management demands archivist competency. However, it also entails commitment from archive digitalization management staff to sustain the life cycle of archives. With such commitment, assigned archivists will consciously integrate personal objectives with organizational ones. In addition, they will be more loyal to organizations and actively partake in attaining the latter objectives. Archivist commitment is notable from their performance quality.

My preliminary observation indicates that dynamic archive management in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo was poor, especially in management systems. The poor management is manifested in 1) The storing system for dynamic archives did not correspond with procedures, 2) A multitude of archives was piled and stored in the warehouse and treated without required standards, 3) Archives were ever-increasing in volume, 4) Technology and social media only acted as distributors of information from dynamic archives, and in so doing, archives received and delivered were out of the supervising unit's reach, 5) No standard operating procedures related to archives were available, 6) No representative warehouse or storing room was in archive storing systems, 7) No archivists were available to favor archive-specific works, 8) Awareness of archive noteworthiness was lacking, 9) Archivist requirements were poorly qualified, and 10) No specified application was available for dynamic archive services at either university or archive-generating unit levels. That is, dynamic archive management entails some changes, particularly in leveraging digitalizing technology for modern archive service activities.

2. Methods

It interpreted and presented data in numbers based on statistical analysis. Three variables examined were archivist competency (X_1) and commitment (X_2) as independent variables and archive digitalization (Y) as the independent one. Data collection was done through observation, questionnaires, and documentation. Data were analyzed using double linear regression.

Figure 1 Research Paradigm

3. Results

3.1. Classical Test Assumption

3.1.1. Data Normality Test

The data normality test was executed using a normal probability plot, the result of which is shown in Figure 2. As shown off in Figure 2, data (dots) were scattered around the diagonal line and following the line orientation. By referring to

the decision-making principle, we concluded that data in the regression model catered to the data normality assumption. Nevertheless, we performed the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test because several data distribution dots were deviant.

Figure 2 The Result of the Normal Probability Plot Test

Table 1 showcases the result of the One-Sample Kolmogorov Smirnov test. As signified in Table1, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z test result of the competency variable was 0.525 at a significance level of 0.946. Considering that the significance from the normality test was higher than alpha 0.05, competency data were normally distributed.

Table 1 The Result of the Data Normality Test

		Competency	Archivist Commitment	Digitalization
N		50	50	50
Normal Parameters ^a	Mean	59.8600	51.2800	43.6800
	Std. Deviation	5.83798	4.86151	5.00384
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.074	0.080	.145
	Positive	0.065	0.068	.115
	Negative	-0.074	-0.080	-.145
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.525	0.562	1.029
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.946	0.910	0.240

Source: Data from SPSS 21 processing, 2022

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z test result of the archivist commitment variable was 0.562 at a significance of 0.910. In that the sig. induced from the normality test was higher than alpha 0.05, archivist commitment data were normally distributed. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z of the archive digitalization variable was 1.029 at a significance of 0.240. On the grounds that the sig. yielded from the normality test was higher than alpha 0.05, archivist commitment data were normally distributed.

3.1.2. Data Multicollinearity Test

Based on previous data processing, we acquired each variable's Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), as suggested in Table 2.

Table 2 The Multicollinearity Test Result

Variable		Collinearity Statistics		Conclusion
		Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)			
	Archivist Competency	0.915	1.093	Non-multicollinearity
	Archivist Commitment	0.915	1.093	Non-multicollinearity

Source: Data from SPSS 21 processing, 2022

As demonstrated in Table 2, the Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) of the archivist competency and commitment variables were 1.093 and 1.093, respectively, at a tolerance of 0.915 and 0.915, respectively. Building on the decision-making determination, if tolerance from the multicollinearity test was higher than > 0.10, there was no multicollinearity, and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was lower than the determined (the number of 10). To sum up, the regression model did not have any multicollinearity issues. That being so, the data fulfilled the multicollinearity test.

3.1.3. Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 3 demonstrates the result of processing data from the heteroscedasticity test. In figure 3, we could observe dots randomly scattered either above or below the number of zero on the Y axis. Therefore, we did not find heteroscedasticity in our model. To bolster the result, we carried out a heteroscedasticity test using the Glejser test.

Figure 3 The Heteroscedasticity Test Result

Table 3 The Heteroscedasticity Test Result

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.766	2.899		3.024	0.004
	Archivist Competency	-0.071	0.038	-0.270	-1.880	0.066
	Archivist Commitment	-0.047	0.050	-0.135	-0.939	0.352

Source: Data from SPSS 21 processing, 2022

Table 3 exhibits the heteroscedasticity test result using the Glejser method. As featured in Table 3, the sig. or probability value (p-value) was 0.066 for the competency variable, and the sig. or probability value (p-value) was 0.352 for the

archivist commitment variable. The value was higher than alpha 0.05. No heteroscedasticity, thus, was found in the model.

3.2. Regression Model Interpretation

Analysis results using SPSS are exhibited in Table 4. The double linear regression model, accordingly, was:

$$\hat{Y} = 6.801 + 0.218X_1 + 0.516X_2 + e$$

Predicated on the regression equation model, a constant was a fixed value. As such, when there was no effect of archivist competency and commitment, archive digitalization was constant, i.e., 6.801 units. The coefficient of regression of the variable X_1 (competency) was 0.218, indicating that a change of one unit in the competency variable would impact archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo by 0.218 units, with the assumption of the archivist commitment variable being constant or *ceteris paribus*. The coefficient of regression of the variable X_2 (archivist commitment) was 0.516, manifesting that a change of one unit in the competency variable would influence archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo by 0.518 units, with the assumption of the archivist commitment variable being constant, or *ceteris paribus*.

Table 4 The Regression Analysis Result

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.801	5.418		1.255	0.216
	Archivist Competency	0.218	0.070	0.322	3.103	0.003
	Archivist Commitment	0.516	0.093	0.572	5.523	0.000

Source: Data from SPSS 21 processing, 2022

3.3. Hypothesis Test

3.3.1. Partial Hypothesis Test

The hypothesis test was conducted using a 95% significance level, or in other words, the sig. (alpha) was 5%. The null hypothesis (H_0) was "There was no effect of archivist competency and commitment on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo", and the alternate hypothesis (H_1) was "There was an effect of archivist competency and commitment on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo". If the t_{count} was higher than the t_{table} , H_0 was rejected. Nonetheless, if the t_{count} was smaller than the t_{table} , H_0 was accepted. Table 5 points out our calculation result using SPSS.

Table 5 The Partial Test Result

Variable	Beta	t_{count}	Sig.
(Constant)		1.255	0.216
Archivist Competency	0.322	3.103	0.003
Archivist Commitment	0.572	5.523	0.000

Source: Data from SPSS 21 processing, 2022

The Effect of Competency on Archive Digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo

Table 5 points out that the t_{count} of the competency variable was 3.103, and the t_{table} , at a 5% significance level and degree of freedom = $n - k - 1$ or $50 - 2 - 1 = 47$, was 1.678. After being compared, the first was higher than the latter ($3.103 > 1.678$). Competency, hence, had a positive and significant effect on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. The positive coefficient presented evidence that competency had a good impact on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.

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Table 5 shows that the t-count of the archivist commitment variable was 5.523, and the t-table, at a 5% significance level and degree of freedom = $n - k - 1$ or $50 - 2 - 1 = 47$, was 1.678. If compared, the t-count was higher than the t-table ($5.573 > 1.678$). Archivist commitment, in so doing, had a positive and significant effect on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. The positive coefficient showed that archivist commitment to archive digitalization had a good impact.

3.3.2. Simultaneous Hypothesis Test

A simultaneous test was done to simultaneously identify the relationship between an independent variable and the dependent one. It was executed using a 95% confidence level, or, in other words, a sig. (alpha) 5%. The null hypothesis (H_0) was "All coefficients of regression were insignificant (the regression model was insignificant)", and the alternate hypothesis (H_1) was "At least one coefficient of regression was significant (the regression model was significant)". If the F_{count} was higher than the F_{table} , H_0 was rejected. Notwithstanding this, if the F_{count} was lower than F_{table} , H_0 was accepted. Table 6 showcases our quantification result using SPSS.

Table 6 The Simultaneous Test Result

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	380.275	2	190.138	27.421	0.000 ^a
	Residual	325.905	47	6.934		
	Total	706.180	49			

Source: Data from SPSS 21 processing, 2022

As signified in Table 6, the F_{count} was 27.421. Meanwhile, the F_{table} , at a 5% significance level and $df_1 = k = 2$ and $df_2 = N - k - 1 = 50 - 2 - 1 = 47$, was 3.195. If being compared, the F_{count} was higher than the F_{table} ($27.421 > 3.195$). That is, archivist competency and commitment had a simultaneous positive and significant effect on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.

3.4. Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination was a value ranging from 0%-77%. Table 7 suggests the coefficient of determination (R^2).

Table 7 The Simultaneous Coefficient of Determination

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.734 ^a	0.538	0.519	2.63328

Source: Data from SPSS 21 processing, 2022

Predicated on Table 7, the R or correlation was 0.734. The R^2 or the coefficient of determination adjusted was 0.519. We deployed the Adjusted R Square of 0.519 to test the effect's degree (the independent variable's ability to explain the dependent one). The figure demonstrated that competency and archivist commitment could explain the archive digitalization by 51.9%, while the rest, namely 48.1%, was explicated by other variables unresearched here, such as archivists' internal factors, e.g., self-awareness and facilities available for archive digitalization.

The test was also carried out by investigating the result of the partial coefficient of determination test. The partial coefficient of determination was employed to test the degree of the partial effect of independent variables on the dependent one. Table 8 exhibits the test result.

Table 7 The Partial Coefficient of Determination

No.	Variable	Rho	Standardized Regression	Partial Determination of Coefficient	
1	Competency	0.489	0.322	0.157	15.7%
2	Archivist Commitment	0.666	0.572	0.381	38.1%
Simultaneous (R Square)				0.538	53.8%

Source: Data from SPSS 21 processing, 2022

Table 7 is laid out in detail as follows:

3.4.1. Archivist Competency

The standardized regression, building on the regression result, was 0.322, and the correlation result was 0.489. Accordingly, the partial coefficient of determination of the competency variable was 0.157, or competency could shed light on the archive digitalization variability by 15.7%.

3.4.2. Archivist Commitment

The standardized regression, predicated on the regression result, was 0.572, and the correlation result was 0.666. The partial coefficient of determination of the archivist commitment variable was, as such, 0.381, or archivist commitment could set forth the archive digitalization variability in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo by 38.1%.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Effect of Archivist Competency on Archive Digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo

Archivists were in need of competency for doing their roles in effective and efficient archive management. Besides, competency was the requirement allowing archivists to implement different methods or abilities in archive management. It was because archivists should be able to execute tasks well as information managers and national cultural heritage keepers. Their existence mattered for the current and next generations. Archivists should perform without discrimination in all forms of manifestation. They should perform wisely and exert archival information for national interests as archivists played a paramount role in all institutions.

Archivists should have at least three basic competencies in managing archives: knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The three aspects could have a positive effect on archivist performance once met. Despite excellent knowledge and skills, archivists would not leave a good impression on their leaders or partners without good attitudes.

From the results of hypothesis 1 (H_1 test), competency had a positive and significant effect on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo at a partial determination of 15.7%. The positive coefficient exhibited that competency had a good impact on archive digitalization management in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. Therefore, archivists should elevate knowledge, skills, and attitudes through various attempts, either through formal or informal education.

Hariyati and Puspasari (2020) conveyed that in Dinas Perpustakaan and Kearsipan in Bojonegoro, staff competency had a positive impact on archive management, as exhibited by the sig. $0.000 < 0.05$ and t_{count} of $5.619 > t_{\text{table}}$ 2.021. Staff competency, thus, had a significant effect on archive management. Furthermore, Bukhori and Laksmi (2019) proposed that archivist competencies featured by knowledge, skill, and attitude indicators influenced archivist performance in ANRI by 56.4%.

An in-depth observation in UPT Kearsipan, UPT Perpustakaan, and UPT Teknologi, Informasi, dan Komunikasi found no employee with relevant educational background, i.e., archival education, in the three institutions. It resulted in a low percentage of the effect of competency on archive digitalization. It was regrettable considering that relevance between education and work activities greatly determined the success level of an objective. It was since relevant education background would afford understanding to individuals before they entered the work world.

Additionally, another factor predisposing employee competency was training participation. Building on profound research, we found that in there were no direct Bimteks “education and training” for digital archive management in three research locations in the last three years. If any, they were only socialization and webinars as regards archive

management (source: official website of UPT Kearsipan). Regrettably, digital archive management was complicated. As such, ones should not rely merely on socialization and webinars associated with archive management if intending to enhance employee competency.

Educational background and training mattered to escalate employee competency. With heightened competencies, employees would be more motivated in performing, yielding more efficient and effective archive management.

4.2. The Effect of Archivist Commitment on Archive Digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo

Commitment contributed to successful archive management. High commitment indicated by archivists was expected to have a continuant effect on archive digitalization. A high commitment was a factor deserving high concern in archive digitalization management. In other words, archivists' excellent and continuant commitment would make archive digitalization management run well, but a lack of commitment would cause digitalization processes to run ineffectively.

Predicated on hypothesis 2 (H₂) test, archivist commitment had a positive and significant effect on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo at a partial determination of 38.1%. The positive coefficient manifested that the higher the archivist commitment, the more successful the archive digitalization management. Institution leaders and other interested parties should continuously improve employee commitment by being mindful of employees' quality of life, prosperity, and work motivation.

As posited by Lubis and Jaya (2019:4), in theoretical or empiric terms, the quality of life, skill, work satisfaction, ethics, motivation, and so on had a positive effect on organizational commitment. Leaders or other interested parties, thus, should increase archivist/employee commitment by prioritizing the factors. A commitment was a determining factor of a successful policy or program. Accordingly, archivist commitment should be inflated to realize continuant archive digitalization.

4.3. The Effect of Archivist Competency and Commitment on Archive Digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo

Archive digitalization served as a response to ever-advanced technology. In addition, it delivered efficiency in archive management. Such efficiency had a positive impact on not only archive management and the internal parties of the institutions concerned but also the community in general. With advanced technology in the form of archive digitalization, the community could access information needed efficiently and without any spatial and temporal constraints.

Manual archive management creating piled files stored in a special room was common. It was archivists' daily menu. With technological advancement, files were not stored in a special room anymore. Instead, they were digitalized to store. Digitalized archives come with some advantages, e.g., they were easy to find, long-storable, resilient, termite-resilient, and loss-resilient unless somebody deleted them. Still, digitalization took a long time to process through cumbersome stages, namely scanning, editing, and uploading. It, accordingly, required competent and committed archivists.

The hypothesis 3 (H₃) test demonstrated that archivist competency and commitment had a simultaneous positive and significant impact on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. The Adjusted R Square was 0.519. The figure exhibited that archivist competency and commitment could shed light on archive digitalization variability by 51.9%, whereas the rest, 48.1%, was spelled out by other variables unresearched here, e.g., facilities and infrastructures to buoy archive digitalization. Other endorsing facilities also determined the success level of digitalization management.

Predicated on my further field study, espousing facilities, such as scanners, were limited in number. UPT Kearsipan and UPT TIK had printers as scanners, but the printers performed poorly. UPT Perpustakaan had scanners which could deal with thick documents. As such, the first two UPTs always faced off challenges when scanning documents in digitalized archive management in the grounds that they only had printers as scanners, and the printers wore out.

In Murtikasari and Arif (2020), Gibson remarked that effective digitalized archive management required facilities and infrastructures. In spite of the excellent competencies and commitment of archivists, without sufficient facilities and infrastructures in accordance with the needs and interests of organizations, archive digitalization would not run effectively. Besides, another factor affecting the success level of archive digitalization was cooperation. According to Asogwa (2012), a collaboration between parties sharing a common interest (objective) contributed to the successful objective achievement. The expertise and skills of individuals were different and depended on what they persevered at. Hence, to confront technological changes and policy implementation as a response to the changes and attain common objectives, a collaboration between different parties from different fields was of importance.

5. Conclusion

- Competency had a positive and significant impact on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo at a partial coefficient of determination of 15.7%. The positive coefficient exhibited that competency had a good implication for archive digitalization management in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. Hence, archivists should promote knowledge, skills, and attitudes through various efforts through either formal or informal education.
- Archivist commitment had a positive and significant influence on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo at a partial coefficient of determination of 38.1%. The positive coefficient featured that the higher the archivist commitment, the more successful the archive digitalization management. In so doing, leaders and other interested parties should continuously scale up employee commitment by paying attention to employee quality of life, welfare, and work motivation.
- Archivist competency and commitment had a simultaneous positive and significant effect on archive digitalization in Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. The Adjusted R Square was 0.519. The figure indicated that 51.9% of archive digitalization variability could be elucidated by archivist competency and commitment, whereas the rest, 48.1%, was explained by other variables unresearched here, e.g., self-awareness, employee satisfaction, work motivation, and facilities available for archive digitalization.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest

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